

Classical Limit of Quantum Mechanics and the Breakdown of $-i\hbar/dx$

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In a classical bound state, conservation of energy: $p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E$ holds for all x . Examined in a statistical sense, one may consider each constant dx to have a probability density proportional to $dt(x)$ where $v(x)=\text{velocity} = dx/ dt(x)$. Thus the particle is followed in time.

In quantum mechanics, even for a free particle $\exp(ipx)$, there exists a wavelength \hbar/p . Within this region one cannot follow the particle in time. In fact, there are two probability distributions $\cos(px)$ and the shifted $\sin(px)$. The two dimensional nature of $\exp(ipx)$ is required to describe the direction of motion.

There exists a mathematical abstraction or average which holds for any x within the wavelength and yields the classical $x = p/m t$. Thus there is a duality, but within a wavelength one cannot follow the particle exactly using $x = p/m t$. Rather there is no time and one thinks of probabilities to be at one x or another. The operator $-i\hbar/dx$ yields the abstracted or average momentum at any x and $(-i\hbar/dx)(-i\hbar/dx)$ average pp if one divides by probability.

In other words: $(-i\hbar/dx) \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) = p$ and $(-i\hbar/dx) (-i\hbar/dx) \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) = pp$. These then apply to any x point. For a bound state, $\exp(ipx)$ is replaced with $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Thus p and $-p$ are included together. From a statistical point of view this is fine because a quantum bound state is described in terms of energy conservation (time-independent Schrodinger equation). Unlike the classical case, the probabilities of p and $-p$ differ, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. The sum $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ yields $\cos(px)$ which is the resolution probability distribution. Taking $-d/dx d/dx$ of $W(x)$ and then dividing by $W(x)$ yields the average kinetic energy at any x within the wavelength. In other words this is the average kinetic energy which matches the classical result for any energy level.

As a result, $\text{prms}(x)\text{prms}(x)/2m + V(x) = E_n$ holds for any quantum level, but $\text{prms}(x)$ is an rms average value which bypasses wave structure. That is why the $\exp(ipx)$ for $p, -p$ and $-i\hbar/dx$ must be used to calculate average quantities within a wavelength. Many different $p, -p$ combinations are needed so that at each x within a wavelength the correct average kinetic energy value appears.

Now consider a high energy level and choose a fixed dx length to represent a tiny region in the system, a cutoff for which there is no further resolution. $p(x)$ is constant within this region. If $\hbar/p \text{prms}(x) \leq dx$, the wave structure of quantum mechanics does not play a role. (Note that for an oscillator, $W(x)$ is a set of crests and troughs with different heights and widths.) As a result, there is no need for d/dx acting on $W(x)$ to describe average kinetic energy within dx . The average kinetic energy is $\text{prms}(x)\text{prms}(x)/2m$ and dx is treated like a point. Only if $\exp(ipx)$ is used does $-i\hbar/dx$ yield the proper classical result. (An alternative scenario is that d/dx acting on a function divided by the function yields the same result as acting on $\exp(ipx)$ divided by $\exp(ipx)$ e.g. $-d/dx d/dx \cos(px)/\cos(px) = -d/dx d/dx \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx)$.)

If one has the quantum kinetic energy expression $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W$ ((1)) and considers one momentum, namely $\text{prms}(x)$, and uses $W(x) = \cos(\text{prms}(x) x)$, then with $\text{prms}(x)$ constant at x , ((1)) yields $\text{prms}(x) \text{prms}(x) / 2m$. Thus d/dx has not broken down even though it does not describe motion within dx which is now a point.

A problem arises, however, if one considers $W_n(x) = W_{n1}(x)W_{n2}(x)$ as this yields an equation containing $dW_1/dx \cdot dW_2/dx / (W_1W_2)$. Then the above procedure yields: $dW_1/dx/W_1 (\text{prms}(x) \sin(\text{prms}(x) x) / \cos(\text{prms}(x) x))$. This does not match the classical value. Furthermore, $dW_2/dx/W_2$ contains $+\text{prms}(x)$ and $-\text{prms}(x)$ with different weights while a classical scenario is $-pP(-p,x) + pP(p,x) = 0$ because $P(-p,x)=P(p,x)$ while quantum mechanically it doesn't. We analyze this situation and conclude that d/dx breaks down/ does not apply in the classical limit because it is used to calculate average values within a wavelength only. It only "works" if the effect of the derivative(s) on a function divided by the function is the same as the effect on $\exp(ipx)$ divided by $\exp(ipx)$.

If a wavelength fits within dx , there is no need to calculate values at any lower x level and d/dx is not needed. In fact, there is a single $\text{prms}(x)$ value in dx and the average time links different dx 's so that one follows the particle (on average in the sense that one ignores structure within each x) by $x(t)$. As a practical consequence, using $-id/dx$ together with the wavefunction $W(x)$ can lead to problems in the classical limit because d/dx does apply. In short, using $-id/dx$ operating on $W_n(x)$ divided by $W_n(x)$ leads to issues unless it produces the same effect as acting on $\exp(ipx)$ divided by $\exp(ipx)$.

Classical Conservation of Energy

A classical bound state may be described by the energy conservation equation:

$$p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((2))$$

which holds for any x . Furthermore the particle is localized in each constant dx which is treated as an x point i.e. dx is associated with a single $x(i)$ and $p(x(i))$ and $V(x(i))$. Given that dx is constant and velocity(x) changes from one dx to another: $v(x) = dx/ dt(x)$. Thus the particle changes in x with corresponding changes in time. No attention is paid to the actual behaviour within dx which seems to contradict ((2)) which describes every x point. The idea seems to be that dx is so small ($\rightarrow 0$) so that it represents a point i.e it is cutoff for resolution.

Quantum Bound State Conservation of Energy

Any quantum bound state has the same conservation equation ((2)) which holds at any x point except for the fact that only a discrete set of E_n are allowed. Furthermore on average $v(x) = dx/dt(x)$ also holds. How does quantum mechanics then differ from the classical result? We consider this in the next section.

Quantum Wavelength and Probabilities

A quantum free particle is described by $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$. Two resolution distributions exist (one shifted from the other) to describe the direction of motion as well as a characteristic wavelength \hbar/p . The modulus of 1 indicates that on average all x points are the same.

A main point, we argue, is that within a wavelength one cannot follow the particle in space and time i.e. $x(t)$. Rather there is no time and the particle is described by the probability $\exp(ipx)$. On average, however, the classical result must hold for any x within the wavelength. Thus there are two sets of physics occurring (i.e. a duality). The probabilistic position description without time within a wavelength is real because it gives rise to experimentally observed diffraction/interference patterns. On average, however, the particle moves as $x = \text{constant } t$ because it must travel from its source to the two slit apparatus and this may be described in terms of an external ruler and clock.

Duality and its Description/Maintenance

How is duality maintained or described? In order to maintain the classical average result at each x point within a wavelength, $-i\hbar/dx$ is used as the momentum operator. This acts on x (an infinite resolution value) because probability $\exp(ipx)$ is a function of any x within the wavelength even though $x = vt$ only holds on average and bypasses the physical probabilistic behaviour. Thus:

$$-i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) = p \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad -\hbar^2/dx^2 \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) = pp \quad ((3b))$$

((3a)) and ((3b)) hold at any x within a wavelength of length \hbar/p . In other words, if dx were to map to a single point (the classical scenario), then $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-ipx)$ would be the corresponding wavefunction.

Given that p and $-p$ have the same pp value, $-\hbar^2/dx^2 [\exp(ipx) \pm \exp(-ipx)] / [\exp(ipx) \pm \exp(-ipx)]$ also gives the same pp .

The Quantum Bound State Scenario

Consider a quantum bound state. Due to duality there must exist an average conservation of energy condition equal to that of classical mechanics i.e.

$$KE(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((4)) \quad \text{for at least some } E_n$$

Instead of using $\exp(ipx)$ to calculate kinetic energy, one notes that $\cos(px)$ from $\exp(ipx)$ is also a kinetic energy eigenstate. Thus one may consider a $p, -p$ pair. The problem is that the wavelength \hbar/p is larger than dx which is chosen to be a small distance in the problem (such that one may ignore any structure within it). Thus one must take an average of different p value $\cos(px)$ terms (for even overall parity). ($\sin(px)$ would be used for odd parity.). Then $-\hbar^2/dx^2$ may be used in a calculation of the average kinetic energy which exists at each x within the crests/troughs of $W(x)$. $W(x)$, like $\cos(px), \sin(px)$ of $\exp(ipx)$ may also have crests/troughs as shown by the quantum oscillator example. These are wider than dx units so a mechanism is needed to map from crest/trough to a point x within. The operator $-i\hbar/dx$ is this mechanism i.e.

$$KE_{\text{classical}}(x) = \frac{1}{2m} p_{\text{rms}}(x)p_{\text{rms}}(x) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W \quad ((4))$$

Here $\text{prms}(x)$ is a root mean square average.

Classical Limit of a Quantum Bound State

Consider now the situation of a high quantum energy level n such that:

$\hbar/\text{prms}(x)$ fits within a chosen dx ((5))

Dx is chosen as a “tiny” length in a system i.e. a cutoff length for resolution. One does not consider details within this length, but maps it to a point $x(i)$ such that there is one velocity $v(x(i))$, one momentum value $p(x(i))$ and one potential value $V(x(i))$ in this region even though $v(x(i))$ changes in value from one dx to another. In this scenario the average time $dt(x)$ spent in each dx differs so $x(t)$ is the description which emerges.

A main point we wish to make is:

If $\hbar/\text{prms}(x) \leq dx$ then there is no need to describe average motion within dx so $-i\hbar/dx$ does not apply or breaks down at this point. (It only applies if acting on $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-ipx)$ divided by this same value. Thus if acting on a different function divided by the function, the same $\exp(ipx)$ result must appear for a classical limit to apply. ((6))

Consider the case of $\hbar/\text{prms}(x)$ fitting within a dx which maps to a single x point. Next use:

$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \rightarrow C \cos(\text{prms}(x) x)$ ((7))

In other words one considers the resolution of a single p value at x . Treating $\text{prms}(x)$ as a constant one may still use $-d/dx$ d/dx to calculate:

$-1/2m \ d/dx \ d/dx \ \cos(px) / \cos(px) = p^2/2m$ where $p = \text{prms}(x)$ ((8))

Using $Wn1(x)Wn2(x)$ to describe $Wn(x)$

A quantum bound state wavefunction $Wn(x)$ may be broken into a product $W1(x)W2(x)$ i.e.

$E_n = E_{n1} + (E_{n2}-E_{n1})$ with $-1/2m \ d/dx \ dW1/dx/W1 + V(x) = E_{n1}$ ((9a))

And $-1/2m \ d/dx \ dW2/dx / W2 - 1/m \ dW1/dx \ dW2/dx / (W1W2) = (E_{n2}-E_{n1})$ ((9b))

Assigning a single p^2 value to ((9b)) i.e. $\cos(p^2 x)$ the first term yields $p^2 p^2/2m$ which is classical. ((9a) using a single p^1 value yields: $p^1 p^1/2m + V(x) = E_{n1}$ which is also classical.

The problem is: $dW2/dx$. For a single p^2 value this yields: $p^2 \sin(p^2 x) / \cos(p^2 x)$ ((10))

((10)) is not a classical result. For example, one may take the classical result:

$p_1 p_1/2m + V(x) = E_1$ and change p_1 to p_1+p_2 to obtain:

$p_1 p_1/2m + V(x) = E_1$ and $p_2 p_2/2m + 1/m p_1 p_2 = E_2 - E_1$ ((11))

Furthermore in the classical limit one has $+prms(x)$ or $-prms(x)$, not both. The average of the two would yield 0 because classically each has the same probability. dW_2/dx is the quantum version of this average, but it is not 0. Thus there is a fundamental problem. In order to use $dW_2/dx/W_2$ one would manually need to replace W_2 with $\exp(i p_2 x)$ as noted in ((6)). In such a case one obtains the classical result, but such a procedure does not follow as a limiting case mathematically i.e. $\cos(px)$ does not automatically separate into $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-ipx)$.

It should be further pointed out that $-idW/dx / W$ is purely imaginary while a classical value must be real. Thus:

$-dW_1/dx dW_2/dx / (W_1 W_2) =$ product of two purely imaginary values while $p_1 p_2$ is the product of two real values ((12))

We caution using d/dx when taking the classical limit. $d/dx d/dx$ seems to be fine when acting on an eigenfunction divided by the eigenfunction because it has the same effect as $d/dx d/dx$ acting on $\exp(ipx)$ divided by $\exp(ipx)$, but if this is not the case there is trouble. We argue that d/dx is used to describe average motion within a wavelength and so when the notion of a wavelength becomes irrelevant due to resolution issues i.e. one or more wavelengths fit into a dx and one does not resolve beyond dx , one may simply assume a $prms(x)$ in dx and bypass using $-id/dx$. In other words classical mechanics is an approximation, not a smooth limit of quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that classical mechanics represents smooth motion/conservation of energy at each point x . It divides the x axis into constant dx pieces, with each mapping to a single x value and hence momentum, velocity, potential value. In other words one cannot resolve any further than dx .

In quantum mechanics, one has wavelengths \hbar/p which are larger than dx . Time is removed and the particle position is described in terms of probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle moving to the right. Nevertheless x is a continuous infinite resolution value and the average classical results must hold as well within a wavelength. Thus there is duality.

In order to facilitate this mapping the operator $-id/dx$ is used for momentum. In other words, it yields classical values which hold at x points within the wavelength. This seems to suggest one should stop using $-id/dx$ if a quantum crest fits within dx . In such a case dx maps to an $x(i)$, $v(x(i))$, $t(x(i))$ etc and there is no wavelength in the picture. For a bound quantum state, $\exp(ipx)$ is replaced by $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. P and $-p$ are used because the kinetic energy

may be given by $\cos(px)$ for a single p , but there is no overall motion so a real $W(x)$ is used. $\exp(ipx)$ is complex only to show overall directional motion.

Quantum mechanically: $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W + V(x) = E_n$. The first term on the LHS is $K_{\text{classical}}(x) = \frac{p_{\text{rms}}(x)^2}{2m}$ for all x . Thus for all x and any energy level, the classical average picture (conservation of average energy) exists, but wavelengths are also present leading to discrete E_n values and a crest/trough scenario for $W_n(x)$ which is physically measurable.

The quantum picture leads to the unusual $-\frac{dW}{dx} / W$ purely imaginary average momentum in quantum mechanics. In classical mechanics this would be 0 or if one forced a direction of motion, i.e. $W \rightarrow \exp(ipx)$, then $-\frac{dW}{dx} / W$ is real and equal to p so has classical meaning, but this does not follow through a limiting process, but is forced.

If $\hbar/p_{\text{rms}}(x) \leq dx$, where dx is a cutoff distance used to describe the limit of resolution, one no longer resolves what happens at lengths smaller than dx . In other words $-\frac{d}{dx}$ which yields results at all x within a wavelength is no longer needed. This is equivalent to stating that quantum effects have been removed. Thus we caution using $-\frac{d}{dx}$ acting on $W_n(x)$ and taking classical limits, because this derivative describes results within dx which are not considered classically.

In this note we have given the example of $W_n(x) = W_{n1}(x)W_{n2}(x)$ and shown that both $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW^2}{dx} / W^2$ and $\frac{dW^2}{dx} / W^2$ appear. If one considers a dx associated with a constant value $p_{\text{rms}}(x)$ and describes W^2 as $\cos(p^2 x)$ (even parity) then $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \cos(p^2 x) / \cos(p^2 x) = \frac{p^2 p^2}{2m}$, but only because this yields the same result as: $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ip^2 x) / \exp(ip^2 x)$ which is the same as mapping each x point to a p^2 .

$\frac{dW^2}{dx} / W^2$ with $W^2 \rightarrow \cos(p^2 x)$, however, leads to $p^2 \sin(p^2 x) / \cos(p^2 x)$ which is not classical. One has to identify $W^2 \rightarrow \exp(ip^2 x)$ (or $-p^2$) to obtain a classical result and this is not the result of a limiting procedure.

In other words if dx is considered to be a cutoff length allowing for no further resolution, then it is mapped to a single x and p value. In such a case, only $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-ipx)$ together with the derivative $-\frac{d}{dx}$ (or products of it) may describe this scenario. A quantum bound wavefunction, however, is real and contains $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ as well as many different $|p|$ values. Even if a limiting process could "pick out" or narrow in on one $|p|$, both p and $-p$ would be present, preventing a proper classical limit. Thus we caution on using the operator $-\frac{d}{dx}$ in classical limit situations. It only seems to work if its effect acting on a function divided by the function is the same as acting on $\exp(ipx)$ divided by $\exp(ipx)$.